

to 76% (see table). In a second observation of three promising lines, yield losses ranged from 66 to 83% and ragged stunt infection ranged from 34 to 74%.

The observations indicate that the disease has the potential to cause severe losses. Further research is needed to identify resistant sources that can be incorporated into commercial varieties. ❧

Occurrence of ufra disease in transplanted rice

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Ufra disease of rice, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, had occurred only in deepwater rice in Bangladesh since Butler first reported it in 1913. During the 1977 aman season, however, ufra was found in transplanted aman rice on the BRRI farm, Joydebpur. The disease appeared in only one experimental field and affected four rice varieties. IR20, Nizersail, and BR4 were severely infested with 70, 80, and 90% affected tillers, respectively. Severe stunting, incomplete panicle emergence, and brown discoloration of boot and flag-leaf bases were observed. The occurrence disproves the previous observation that ufra disease is confined to deepwater rice. Under favorable conditions it may affect other rice crops. ❧

Monthly fluctuation in number of conidia of rice blast fungus trapped by spore sampler

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In 1976 and 1977, a disease nursery was established for epidemiologic studies of rice blast in the field in the first and second rice crops. The rice varieties Tainan 5 (moderately resistant to neck blast) and Chianon shen 8 (susceptible) were grown at a 20- × 25-cm spacing in four equal plots of 6 × 8 m divided by

crossing lines. The varieties were alternated; each variety occupied two nonadjoining plots. The experimental field was given a standard fertilizer treatment — 120-60-50kg/ha of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O, respectively. An automatic Kramar-Collins spore sampler was placed at the center of the experimental field to collect conidia the year round. Samples were taken 4 times/hour for a total of 6 minutes; the total air volume was 120 liters. The first crop was transplanted in late January and harvested in early June; the second crop was transplanted in late July and harvested in early November.

In both years, the number of trapped conidia was highest in April and August, in the first and second crops (see table). The peaks in trapped conidia coincided with the peaks of leaf blast in 1976 and 1977. But no conidia were trapped in

Number of conidia of rice blast fungus trapped monthly in 1976 and 1977 in the field. Chia-yi Agricultural Experiment Station, Taiwan.

Month	Conidia (no.) trapped in	
	1976	1977
January	0	0
February	0	0
March	651	13
April	4,544	818
May	695	162
June	111	19
July	43	103
August	749	497
September	45	303
October	39	15
November	14	0
December	0	0

January, February, or November 1977, or in December of 1976 or 1977. That probably indicates that the rice blast fungus overwintered for 3 to 4 months in Taiwan. ❧

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Brachmia arotrae, a leaf folder of rice in India

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Caterpillars of *Brachmia arotrae* sp. were observed folding and damaging rice leaves at the Central Rice Research Institute farm, Cuttack, in November and December 1977. The adult is smaller than *C. medinalis* and pale straw in color. Eggs are light yellow, flat, and oval, laid singly on the leaves or, occasionally, in rows. The incubation period is 4 to 5 days. The fully grown larva has a black head and prothoracic shield and is about 10 mm long. It folds the leaves and feeds on the epidermis from inside the folded leaf. About a month is required to complete one generation. The pest, along with *C. medinalis*, was abundant in late-planted crops and accounted for 30 to 40% of the leaf folder population during the first week of December at Cuttack. Both *C. medinalis* and

B. arotrae were also found infesting the weed *Leersia hexandra*. *C. medinalis* and *B. arotrae* were found to be parasitized by *Apanteles* sp. and *Brachmeria* sp.

Brachmia arotrae is becoming increasingly important. It was also observed in certain parts of Madurai district of Tamil Nadu; it may now be fairly well distributed in India. It appears to have missed the attention of rice researchers in India, perhaps because its damage closely resembles that from *C. medinalis*. ❧

Nematodes in paddy fields of Pakistan

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Nematodes damage the paddy crop in many rice-growing areas of the world. Nematode species found in Pakistan are *Aphelenchoides* sp., *Criconemoides* sp., *Ditylenchus* sp., *Helicotylenchus*

erythrinae, *Hemicycliophora* sp., *Hemicriconemoides* spp., *Hirschmanniella oryzae*, *Hoplolaimus* sp., *Pratylenchus* sp., and *Tylenchorhynchus* spp. The most important are *H. erythrinae*, *H. oryzae*, *Hoplolaimus*, and *Tylenchorhynchus*. *H. oryzae* is widely distributed and abundant. During feeding it moves in the root system of the host plant and dissolves its cell walls, forming large cavities that affect the efficient

functioning of the root system during heavy infestations. The population of this nematode increases with increasing age of the standing crop.

Hoplolaimus sp. occurs in comparatively low numbers. It damages the parenchymatous cells, which retards plant growth. *Tylenchorhynchus* spp., and *H. erythrinae* are widely distributed in Pakistan but have variable populations. They damage mostly the cortex,

therefore their feeding has less impact than that of other species. White tip disease of rice caused by *Aphelenchoides besseyi* has not been recorded in Pakistan, but it is widespread elsewhere.

Nematode damage seems to depend on the population, intra- and inter-specific competition, reproductive rates, and environmental factors. Exact losses caused by nematodes in Pakistan's paddy crop are not known.

Rice hispa found on wheat in the Punjab, India

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The rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* causes considerable damage to rice in parts of Gurdaspur, Amritsar, Hoshiarpur, and Kapurthala districts in Punjab state, India. The insect breeds actively from

May to October, then overwinters, probably in the adult stage.

In early March 1978, rice hispa attacked the wheat cultivar WG 357 at the Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala. The overall damage was not serious; from 3 to 6 adults/10 m² were recorded. By the end of March, the insect also appeared in the summer rice nursery; 2 to 4 adults/seedling were observed. During the off-season, a limited survey of wild grasses and weeds at the research station showed no rice

hispa. A more detailed and extensive survey is needed to establish the insect's overwintering habits.

The finding of rice hispa on wheat is especially significant in the Punjab, where rice and wheat are generally rotated. If the insect can establish on wheat as well as on rice, it may become more serious because food material will be available to it year round. Efforts to grow two crops of rice per year may further accentuate the hispa problem.

A new enemy of *Azolla*

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The aquatic fern *Azolla pinnata* is being recommended for incorporation into rice fields as a natural source of fertilizer. Its cultivation is gaining momentum among rice farmers because of its ability to fix

atmospheric nitrogen symbiotically with blue-green algae. *Azolla* is estimated to fix from 30 to 35 kg N/ha within 20 days.

Studies at the College of Agriculture, Vellayani, show that such pests as lepidopterous larvae and snails (gastropoda) are major factors limiting *Azolla* propagation. The phytophagous gastropods damage the fern more severely than the caterpillars do.

The snails feed voraciously on the fern at the edge of the paddy, close to the water surface. They sometimes move to the water just below the floating *Azolla* and devour the fern, but do not feed on rice plants. The pest spreads fairly rapidly.

Phorate (10 G) applied at the recommended dosage of 12.5 kg/ha for insect control also controlled the snails.

Outbreak of rice caseworm and brown planthopper in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India

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The rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*, previously a minor rice pest in the Periyar Vaigai River Project of Tamil Nadu, assumed major importance in single-cropped areas of Madurai district

in December 1977. The high yielding variety IR20 is widely grown in those tracts. The planting season usually begins in September and October. Infestation was severe in rice that was transplanted later. Patches of cut and scraped leaf surfaces and withered plants were prominent.

The brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, which was earlier considered a minor pest in that area, has become serious since the introduction of high yielding dwarf varieties such as IR8 and

IR20. Infestation was heavy in 1973 and 1974. It was also severe in several parts of Melur and Vellalore in December 1977. The varieties IR20 and Bhavani were infested in the flowering and maturity stages and severely hopperburned. The outbreak may have been caused by the introduction of fertilizer-responsive, high-tillering rice varieties; heavy fertilizer applications; closer plant spacings; and indiscriminate use of pesticides.